

A MODEL FOR DIAGNOSING PATIENTS WITH VIRAL PNEUMONIA BASED ON THE SIR MODEL.

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At the end of 2019, a coronavirus infection was detected in the city of Wuhan of the People’s Republic of China. The causative agent of the disease was temporarily named 2019-nCoV. The disease has spread to more than 170 countries. The World Health Organization (WHO) gave an official name to this infection on February 11, 2020 and called it the new coronavirus - COVID-19 (“Coronavirus disease 2019”) and announced the COVID-19 pandemic on March 11, 2020. Worldwide, 702,606,787 cases and 6,977,119 deaths have been identified. Despite the peak of detection of the disease in the world, a decrease in the number of detected cases was not observed for a long time. The risk of complications and death of COVID-19 depends on the severity of the clinical manifestations of the disease, the incidence of severe forms reaches 14%-19%.

This article discusses the SIR (susceptible-infectious-recovery) model and how it can be modeled.

Using the SIR model, the entire population is divided into 3 groups according to their concept, depending on the status of the infection under consideration:

In the SIR model, these groups are:

S - susceptible (susceptible, that is, without immunity and can be infected),

I - infectious (infectious),

R - Restored.

N-population. Population is $N=S+I+R$.

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dS}{dt} = -\frac{\beta SI}{N} \\ \frac{dI}{dt} = \frac{\beta SI}{N} - \gamma I \\ \frac{dR}{dt} = \gamma I \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

One of the important results of the study was the introduction of the infection rate index, which is the most important characteristic of the disease and the parameter of the spread of the epidemic.

$$R_0 = \frac{\beta}{\gamma} \quad (2)$$

R_0 is the index of infection.

The SIR model describes the population change of each of these divisions in terms of two parameters, β and γ .

β - describes the intensity of infection: an infected person comes into contact with bN .

γ - the average recovery rate: i.e. $1/\gamma$ - the average period of time an infected person can spend it (Fig. 1.1).

Figure 1.1. Schematic of the SIR model.

The following combines these equations for a disease characterized by parameters $b = 0.2$, $1/\gamma = 10$ days in $N = 1000$ population (perhaps a school flu). The model starts with one infected person on day 0:

The statistical indicators presented above show the parameters of the three groups of the disease in terms of the percentage of the population and the number of days, that is, the level of susceptibility to the disease decreases within 160 days, the number of patients increases between 60-70 days, and the number of those recovered with immunity increases (Fig. 1.2).

Figure 1.2. Statistical parameters of the disease of COVID-19 in the SIR model Conclusion.

The advantage of using differential models to describe the spread of an epidemic (including COVID-19) is to take into account the characteristics of the infection. Such models describe the outbreak qualitatively, but lack sufficient flexibility. Taking into account the change in the parameters describing the restrictive measures, new mutations of the virus lead to specificity and instability.

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